

The Taliban's Neo-Old Afghanistan: Humanitarian Crisis and Emerging Refugee Problem

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Abstract: After a long period of twenty years, America has decided to stop the operations of USA in Afghanistan. And their army retreated. As soon as the US withdrew, the Taliban seized power in Afghanistan. The Taliban formed their government in Afghanistan through some violence. With the arrival of the Taliban, many Afghans and various minorities began to seek refuge in various countries to defend themselves, and many were internally displaced. Instability in Afghanistan is harmful and dangerous not only for the countries of South Asia but also for the entire world. Afghanistan has been unstable for the past several decades, but the arrival of the Taliban has created a new and frightening problem in the South Asian region. The current situation in Afghanistan is reminiscent of the geopolitical problems of the 1990s. Internal war, violence, disease, resistance to modernism, old religious traditions, economic, political, social, religious minority problems, health problems, education problems, gender discrimination, feeling of insecurity, patriarchal government etc. are causing internal displacement of people in Afghanistan. Or being forced to accept refuge outside the country thus creating a major humanitarian crisis.

Keyword: Taliban-USA, Insecurity, Humanitarian Aid, Refugee, Displaced, UNHCR

Introduction:

In 1994, a group of radicalized students who received religious training in a refugee camp in Pakistan took control of the city of Kandahar and began to seize power. This group was known as the Taliban. By 1998, almost all of Afghanistan was under Taliban control. The Taliban were a group of extremists who strictly enforced Sharia law in Afghanistan, women were deprived of education, girls were not allowed to go to school, women were not allowed to work, overall, the Taliban became a safe haven for international terrorists. Only Pakistan, UAE and Saudi Arabia recognized the Taliban. To put an end to terrorism, the USA and its allies ousted the Taliban regime in 2001.

Taliban's Neo-Old Afghanistan:

For almost twenty years from 2001 to 2021, the common people of Afghanistan could enjoy independence, gender equality, education, health, employment, etc. And an environment conducive to development was being created. once again in 2021, a vacuum was created by the departure of USA in Afghanistan. And the Taliban once again seized power. The current situation has created the same problems that occurred in the 1990s that will recur in Afghanistan.

The old Afghanistan was under the Taliban rule in the 1990s and now the new Afghanistan of 2021 which is again under the Taliban rule. For nearly twenty years, the extremist religious ideology of the terrorist Taliban was successfully suppressed in Afghanistan. During this twenty-year period, Afghanistan underwent drastic changes, including girls' schooling, women working openly, and development without Sharia

law. During these twenty years, emphasis was placed on education, health institutions and economic sector was continued, ideological

modernization was created, efforts were made to create harmony between the people and the government, non-violence and peaceful development ideologies were encouraged, international financial funds were used for the development of the weaker sections. So, today's Afghanistan is not what it was twenty years ago. The people of today's Afghanistan seem to be moving towards steady development and modernity along with religion. Economic, social, health, education, poverty, available means of livelihood. Such various problems are faced by common people. But the coming to power of the Afghan Taliban is emphasizing how the Afghanistan of the 1990s can be imposed on the country by religious Sharia law.

Humanitarian Crisis:

International financial aid organizations withdrew from Afghanistan. Also, financial crisis faced the Taliban. It became impossible to pay employees, the public health system was completely destroyed. The recent war has created various humanitarian crises. And the possibility of renewed violence arose. In addition, the people living in the urban areas of Afghanistan became unable to earn their own livelihood, while the situation in the rural areas became extremely fragile and miserable.

After the withdrawal of American troops, the Taliban government came to power in Afghanistan, but various problems arose in front of Afghanistan when they came to power. Issues such as health, hunger, employment, livelihoods and several million people's livelihoods

depended on international aid funds, but that too came to a halt with the arrival of the Taliban. Afghanistan's foreign financial assets were also frozen. Ongoing conflict, natural disasters, poverty, food shortages, pandemics like Covid-19 and sudden power transitions, violence and instability by the Taliban in August 2021 have disrupted the lives of people in Afghanistan and displaced many internally. This also put pressure on countries that aid in humanitarian crises. According to the UN, nearly 3.5 million people were internally displaced by the end of 2021, and at least 2.7 million were forced to take refuge across borders involuntarily. Afghanistan has the third largest number of displaced people in the world after Syria and Venezuela. 1.3 million and 780,000 registered Afghani refugees live in Pakistan and Iran respectively.¹

Millions of people in Afghanistan are in need of humanitarian aid due to the past twenty to forty years of war, frequent natural disasters, political turmoil, extreme poverty, drought and, of course, the Corona pandemic. After the arrival of the Taliban, only poverty and unemployment remain as people have no money to buy food. But the Taliban did not think about how to save the economy from collapse. On the other hand, different conditions under the Sharia Law such as how women should wear clothes, women should not leave the house, women should not work, girls should not take school education, are being announced day by day by the Taliban. A resolution was passed by the UN Security Council that the Taliban will allow people who want to leave the country to do so, and will not obstruct the delivery of humanitarian aid, violate human rights, and not commit coercion or crimes against women and children.²

Before the arrival of the Taliban, Afghanistan was dependent on international financial aid, with nearly 38 million people dependent on foreign aid. But after the hard-line Islamist faction of the Taliban seized power, foreign aid stopped. How will ordinary citizens, Afghan women and girls, journalists, academics, human rights activists, ethnic communities, religious communities and other minority groups be protected under Taliban rule? Now there is a question mark on this. Due to insecurity and violence, the lives of women and girls have become very insecure and dire. People are faced with shelter, food, water, and health needs.

According to a survey conducted by the United Nations World Food Program, almost 98 percent of people in Afghanistan do not have enough food to eat. The political transition has had a major impact on the country's basic services,

financial system as well as the market, and the lives of millions of people have rapidly shifted towards poverty, with the number doubling in 2022 from 2021. By 2022, nearly 97 percent of the population will be below the poverty line. Humanitarian organizations are also facing difficulties in assisting such a large population. As soon as a terrorist organization named Taliban took over the power of Afghanistan, the peace that had developed for a few decades was again disturbed and Afghanistan was broken again and people's lives began to fall. The advent of the Taliban has resulted in a massive increase in violence, war, pauperisation, degradation, fear, unrest, violence against women and girls, resulting in millions of people being internally displaced and many fleeing the country out of fear and taking refuge in various neighbouring nations. Afghanistan began to pose a global refugee problem. It is also beginning to affect neighbouring nations and regional security. The humanitarian crisis caused by the negative impact of the Taliban in Afghanistan. The Taliban had a negative impact on Education, Safety-security, Hunger, Water, Health, Economic, women, Children, Adult, Hazara ethnic and religious population, various tribes.

Taliban's Sharia and Women: The Taliban want strict implementation of Sharia law. Public hanging or mutilation, forcing men to grow beards, forcing women to wear veils, banning music, cinema and television, not allowing a girl above the age of ten to attend school. Women should not go out alone. The fate of women in Afghanistan is desperate, hopeless, unbearable, and disgraced. Women are imprisoned in a cloth prison called Burkha. After taking power, the Taliban continued the system of gender apartheid, stripping them of all their human rights, including the right to work, education, health care, and speech. Women and girls cannot be examined by a male doctor. It is also prohibited to employ women doctors or nurses in hospitals. Women can be brutally beaten and abused, publicly flogged and even sentenced to death if they disobey the Taliban's orders. Instead of the woman, the man of her household can also be punished.

Emerging Refugee Problem:

In the period leading up to the unexpected arrival and seizure of power by the Taliban, instability and violence escalated in Afghanistan, with covid pandemic, extreme poverty, inadequate food, epidemics, natural disasters, economic poverty, lack of health facilities, poor education environment, and starvation. And as a result, nearly several million

people were internally displaced or forced to flee the country.

After the Taliban seized power, thousands of refugees fled to the United States for their lives, Greece built a wall along its border with Turkey to prevent Afghan refugees from entering Greece. Refugees of Afghanistan started turning to different countries for refuge. In that, many people fled in neighbouring Iran, Pakistan and Turkey. After Turkey, Greece and after Greece, the number of refugees also started to increase in the countries of Europe. In order to prevent the increase of refugees and terrorism in Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan in Central Asia, the Central Asian countries have already started making agreements with the Taliban, including Russia. China-Pakistan Economic Corridor and Geopolitical Significance of Afghanistan, Also, The SAARC, TAPI natural gas pipeline and India's interest are important, that is why Afghanistan is considered to be an important territory under the control of the Taliban for various reasons. South Asian nations have not signed the 1951 Convention on Refugees and the 1967 Protocol Relating to the Status of Refugees. The number of Afghan refugees also started increasing in India. India has also made provision for six-month e-visa. It is also feared that the arrival of the Taliban will lead to the emergence of terrorist organizations like Lashkar-e-Taiba and Jaish-e-Mohammed. Regional stability is also threatened by terrorism and immediate security threat. Only a stable government in Afghanistan can provide a stable economy and stop displacement and migration. But the Taliban does not seem to be the right choice for Afghanistan. Therefore, international organizations should focus on solving this problem. It is necessary to provide immediate humanitarian financial assistance to Afghanistan. All nations of the United Nations must decide together how to maintain peace, order and stability in Afghanistan.

Literature Review:

A brief overview of the studies done in the context of topic some of the reviewed studies below:

- 1) **Donini, A. (2009). Afghanistan: Humanitarianism under threat. Feinstein International Center, Tufts University, Medford, MA.**

This briefing paper discusses the humanitarian challenges and opportunities in Afghanistan. Afghanistan is a serious threat to humanitarian conflict. insecurity and terrorism are contributing factors. The authors also suggest how to build and harmonize humanitarian consensus.

- 2) **UNAMA Human rights service. (2022). Human Rights in Afghanistan 15 August 2021 – 15 June 2022.**

The United Nations Assistance Mission in Afghanistan (UNAMA) released a report on the torture and ill-treatment of Afghan citizens, extrajudicial detention, extrajudicial killings, protection of civilians, rights of women and girls, forced displacement, fundamental freedoms, and the treatment of civilians by the Taliban. Concern has been expressed.

- 3) **United Nations Development Programme. (2021, September 9). 97 Percent of Afghans Could Plunge into Poverty by Mid 2022 [Press Release]. <https://www-dev.undp.org/geneva/press-releases/97-percent-afghans-could-plunge-poverty-mid-2022-says-undp>**

According to a UNDP press note published in 2021, nearly 97 percent of Afghanistan's population will fall into poverty by June 2022 due to economic crisis. It was pointed out that vulnerable people and communities in Afghanistan are in urgent need of humanitarian financial assistance. To protect women and girls, to develop local livelihoods, basic income and infrastructure an economic package was proposed but even today there is no solution to Afghanistan's poverty and hunger.

- 4) **United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA) Afghanistan. (2021). Afghanistan Humanitarian Fund Annual Report 2021**

The arrival of the Taliban in 2021 has increased conflict, violence, war-like conditions, strangulation of human rights. inadequate supply of food led to malnutrition among girls and women. Also, the International Development Fund was affected. The Taliban seize power, leading to economic crisis, instability and widespread hunger in the country. According to the report, nearly 24.4 million people are in need of humanitarian assistance by the end of 2022.

Objective of Study:

- Critically analysing the poor living conditions in contemporary Afghanistan and highlighting the lives of people under the control of the Taliban.
- Understanding the urgent need for humanitarian aid and studying the role of the Taliban in driving the growing refugee crisis.
- Exploring economic, political, religious, causes of unstable Afghanistan. To study the factors driving population migration abroad. seeking refuge in a new country.

Scope of the Study:

The scope of the proposed study will not be limited to only Afghanistan's instability; it will also have a direct impact on Iran, central Asia, and south Asia. It will indirectly have an impact on western nations, including the USA, in terms of geopolitical strategic interest and human security (refugees and terrorism). The study aims to comprehend the underlying causes of the complex issues faced by refugees, internally displaced people, and asylum seekers from Afghanistan. It covers on a number of the Afghan people's issues, including those that are religious, social, educational, political, economic, physical, psychological, and legal, which drive them to seek refuge.

Research Methodology:

Descriptive, analytical and exploratory research design has been used while studying the subject. We can call it descriptive because it displays a clear and accurate picture of the economic, socio-religious, geographical conditions and past customs of the people of Afghanistan, as well as numerous aspects and difficulties among the people that encourage them to flee and seek refuge. The study is based on secondary data. Collected from various sources like, newspapers, Lok Sabha debates, various libraries, institutes, government offices and reports published by them, journals, manuals, published books, articles, magazines, internet and past research reports, documentation of working NGOs.

Suggestion and Recommendation:

- The Taliban should be pressured to meet international human rights protections in Afghanistan through various regional and international organizations and UN.
- The problem of Afghanistan cannot be solved only with humanitarian financial aid but the economy of Afghanistan needs to be strengthened and for that the international community needs to negotiate with the Taliban.
- The Taliban must respect the rights of women and girls and ensure gender equality in accordance with international humanitarian law.
- Through the United Nations, Afghanistan's frozen money in various countries should be used to address humanitarian issues.

Conclusion of the Study:

Accepting financial aid is not a permanent solution, although it is an immediate need to help refugees. Once the political situation in Afghanistan stabilizes, economic life will get a chance to improve. A lot depends on the way the Taliban are treated by the common man and how the Taliban presents itself in international fora.

International recognition is the backbone of Afghanistan's economy. If economic transformation does not occur, and violent instability continues, civil war may break out. Economic weakness and instability may lead to the emergence of new terrorist groups. Afghans will flee from their own country and become a major problem (refugee crisis) for the international community in the coming years. Therefore, the Taliban must give the common population the right to live in peace and security, without discrimination on the basis of race, religion, and sex, without torture, cruel and degrading treatment, enslavement, as stipulated in international humanitarian law. So that new refugees can be prevented from being created.

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